

WindCube®

Pioneering wind lidar development

2006

1.0

2010

2.0

2019

2.1

2025

2.1 XP

[Extended Performance]

+500

Organizations using
WindCube products

+3000

Units delivered

WindCube 2.1 XP addresses key challenges

Covers the full rotor sweep height up to 400m

Less uncertainty

More data availability

Connected instrument with Vaisala Compass cloud solution

Challenges for the future

"Turbulence is the most important unsolved problem of classical physics."

– Prof. Richard Feynman (1964)

... and for wind lidar !

Wind lidar standards for TI

Wind lidar TI measurement

Wind lidar measurement in complex terrain

